

CO₂ emissions from SOC change are calculated based on results from the SALUS simulation (see Equation (1)).

$$\Delta\text{SOC}_j = \frac{(\text{SOC}_{j,f} - \text{SOC}_{j,0})}{30} \cdot \frac{44}{12} \quad (1)$$

where ΔSOC_j is the SOC sequestration rate per hectare on the j^{th} parcel ($\text{kgCO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$). SOC_j is SOC level on the j^{th} parcel in a given year (kgC ha^{-1}). Subscripts 0 and f indicate the initial and final years, respectively. N₂O emissions are estimated by the Tier 1 method in the IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories¹, including N₂O from nitrogen fertilizer, dead biomass residues and SOC loss (see Equations (2a-2e)). For accuracy, N₂O emissions from biomass residues and SOC loss for each parcel are calculated based on the annual values. Average N₂O emissions are used in the GHG calculations.

$$\text{AVGGHG}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}_j} = \frac{\sum_i^{30} \text{GHG}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}_{j,i}}}{30} \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{GHG}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}_{j,i}} = \text{GHG}_{\text{N-input}_j} + \text{GHG}_{\text{N-SOC}_{j,i}} + \begin{cases} \text{GHG}_{\text{CROP}_{j,i}} & \text{for the first year of the planting cycle} \\ 0 & \text{for otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2b)$$

$$\text{GHG}_{\text{N-input}_j} = F_{\text{SN}} \cdot (\text{EF}_1 + \text{Frac}_{\text{GASF}} \cdot \text{EF}_4 + \text{Frac}_{\text{LEACH}} \cdot \text{EF}_5) \cdot \frac{44}{28} \cdot 265 \quad (2c)$$

$$\text{GHG}_{\text{N-SOC}_{j,i}} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } (\text{SOC}_{j,i-1} - \text{SOC}_{j,i}) < 0 \\ (\text{SOC}_{j,i-1} - \text{SOC}_{j,i}) \cdot \frac{1}{R} \cdot (\text{EF}_1 + \text{Frac}_{\text{LEACH}} \cdot \text{EF}_5) \cdot \frac{44}{28} \cdot 265 & \text{for } (\text{SOC}_{j,i-1} - \text{SOC}_{j,i}) \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2d)$$

$$\text{GHG}_{\text{CROP}_{j,i}} = \frac{Y_{j,i}}{0.65} \cdot (0.35 \cdot N_{\text{AG}} + R \cdot N_{\text{BG}}) \cdot (\text{EF}_1 + \text{Frac}_{\text{LEACH}} \cdot \text{EF}_5) \cdot \frac{44}{28} \cdot 265 \quad (2e)$$

where $\text{AVGGHG}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}_j}$ is the average N₂O emissions ($\text{kgCO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$) on the j^{th} parcel, and $\text{GHG}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}_{j,i}}$ is N₂O emissions on the j^{th} parcel in the i^{th} year ($\text{kgCO}_2 \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$). $\text{GHG}_{\text{N-input}_j}$ is N₂O emissions from nitrogen fertilizer on the j^{th} parcel, and $\text{GHG}_{\text{N-SOC}_{j,i}}$ is N₂O emissions from SOC loss on the j^{th} parcel in the i^{th} year. $\text{GHG}_{\text{CROP}_{j,i}}$ is N₂O emissions from dead biomass residues from the previous planting cycle on the j^{th} parcel in the i^{th} year. F_{SN} is the amount of nitrogen fertilizer applied ($\text{kgN ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$). $\text{Frac}_{\text{GASF}}$ is a fraction of nitrogen fertilizer that volatilizes as NH₃ and NO_x ($=0.11^1$), and $\text{Frac}_{\text{LEACH}}$ is that fraction of all nitrogen added that is lost through leaching and runoff ($=0.24^1$). EF_1 is an emission factor for N₂O emissions from N inputs ($=0.01^1$), and EF_4 is an emission factor for N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N on soils and water surfaces ($=0.01^1$). EF_5 is an emission factor for N₂O emissions from N leaching and runoff ($=0.011^1$). R is the C:N ratio of SOC ($=15^1$), and $Y_{j,i}$ is biomass yield on the j^{th} parcel in

¹ IPCC 2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories; IPCC: 2019.

the i^{th} year (dry kg ha⁻¹ year⁻¹). In the SALUS simulation, 65% of above-ground biomass is assumed to be harvested. N_{AG} is the N content of above-ground residues (=0.015 for perennial grasses¹), and N_{BG} is the N content of below-ground residues (=0.012¹). RS is a ratio of below-ground biomass to above-ground biomass (=0.8¹).

GHG emissions of switchgrass production, $GHG_{\text{switchgrass}}$ (kgCO₂ Mg⁻¹), is

$$GHG_{\text{switchgrass}} = \frac{(\Delta SOC_j + AVGGHG_{N_2O_j} + GHG_{\text{fuel}} + GHG_{\text{inputs}})}{\text{Yield}} \quad (3)$$

Where GHG_{fuel} is the GHG emissions associated with fuel used in field operations (e.g., spreading, baling, etc., kgCO₂ ha⁻¹). GHG_{inputs} is the GHG emissions associated with agronomic inputs (e.g., agrochemicals and fertilizers, kgCO₂ ha⁻¹). Yield is available switchgrass per hectare (dry Mg ha⁻¹).

GWI of biofuel derived from switchgrass, GWI (gCO₂ MJ⁻¹) is

$$GWI = \frac{GHG_{\text{switchgrass}}}{Y_{\text{bio}} \cdot (1 - \text{Loss})} + GHG_{\text{transport}} + GHG_{\text{storage}} + GHG_{\text{biorefinery}} + GHG_{\text{dis/com}} \quad (4)$$

where $GHG_{\text{transport}}$ and GHG_{storage} are GHG emissions of transport and storage (gCO₂ MJ⁻¹), respectively. $GHG_{\text{biorefinery}}$ is GHG emissions associated with biorefinery, including material inputs, process emissions and GHG credit of excess electricity (gCO₂ MJ⁻¹). $GHG_{\text{dis/com}}$ is GHG emissions associated with distribution and combustion of biofuel (gCO₂ MJ⁻¹). Y_{biofuel} is biofuel yield (dry Mg MJ⁻¹). Loss is the loss fraction during transport and storage.